

Collective Mind: toward a common language to facilitate reproducible research and technology transfer

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github.com/mlcommons/ck

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Abstract

During the past 10 years, we have considerably improved the reproducibility of experimental results from published papers by introducing the artifact evaluation process with a unified artifact appendix and reproducibility checklists, Jupyter notebooks, containers, and Git repositories. On the other hand, our experience reproducing more than 200 papers shows that it can take weeks and months of painful and repetitive interactions between teams to reproduce artifacts. This effort includes decrypting numerous README files, examining ad-hoc artifacts and containers, and figuring out how to reproduce computational results. Furthermore, snapshot containers pose a challenge to optimize algorithms' performance, accuracy, power consumption and operational costs across diverse and rapidly evolving software, hardware, and data used in the real world.

In this article, we will explain how our practical artifact evaluation experience and the feedback from researchers and evaluators motivated us to develop a simple, intuitive, technology agnostic, and English-like scripting language called Collective Mind (CM). It helps to automatically adapt any given experiment to any software, hardware, and data while automatically generating unified README files and synthesizing modular containers with a unified API. It is being developed by MLCommons to facilitate reproducible AI/ML Systems research and minimizing manual and repetitive benchmarking and optimization efforts, reduce time and costs for reproducible research, and simplify technology transfer to production. We will also present several recent use cases of how CM helps MLCommons, the Student Cluster Competition, and artifact evaluation at ACM/IEEE conferences. We will conclude with our development plans, new challenges, possible solutions, and reproducibility and optimization challenges powered by the MLCommons Collective Knowledge Playground and CM: access.cKnowledge.org.

Keywords: *machine learning, systems, portability, reproducibility, reusability, automation, reusable best practices, portable MLOps, MLSysOps, DevOps, portable workflows, collaborative benchmarking, optimization, software/hardware/model co-design, recipes, productivity, collective knowledge, open API*

1 CM and CK history

1.1 Collective Knowledge v1 and v2 (CK)

The open-source Collective Knowledge Technology v1 and v2 (CK) [3] was originally developed by Grigori Fursin. CK development was based on Grigori's long experience helping the community reproduce many research projects and validate them in the real world across diverse and continuously changing models, data sets, software and hardware since 2013 [2].

CK development was also sponsored by cTuning.org, HiPEAC and OctoML.

The archive of this discontinued framework is available at github.com/mlcommons/ck/tree/master/ck.

1.2 MLCommons Collective Mind (CM)

Grigori donated the CK technology to MLCommons.org in 2022 to benefit everyone, developed a prototype of a new version of CK called Collective Mind (CM) from scratch, and helped establish the MLCommons Task Force on Automation and Reproducibility co-chaired with Arjun Suresh [1].

This collaborative effort resulted in an automated CM workflow to run MLPerf inference benchmarks with the great help, feedback and contributions from the community [5, 4].

CM is now officially supported, developed and maintained by MLCommons.org with the help from cKnowledge.org and cTuning.org.

Go to the GitHub development websites for more details: github.com/mlcommons/ck and github.com/mlcommons/cm4mlps.

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References

- [1] MLCommons Task Force on Automation and Reproducibility co-chaired by Grigori Fursin and Arjun Suresh. <https://github.com/mlcommons/ck/blob/master/docs/taskforce.md>, 2022–current.
- [2] Grigori Fursin. ACM TechTalk’21: Reproducing 150 Research Papers and Testing Them in the Real World: Challenges and Solutions. <https://learning.acm.org/techtalks/reproducibility>, 2021.
- [3] Grigori Fursin. Collective knowledge: organizing research projects as a database of reusable components and portable workflows with common interfaces. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 379(2197):20200211, 2021.
- [4] Grigori Fursin. Toward a common language to facilitate reproducible research and technology transfer: challenges and solutions. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8105339>, 2023.
- [5] Grigori Fursin. cKnowledge playground GUI to run MLPerf inference benchmarks using the MLCommons CM automation framework. <https://access.cknowledge.org/playground/?action=howtorun>, 2024.